

Framing Theory, Political Speeches and Nigerian Newspapers

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Abstract

Framing is fast gaining research attention in communication and media studies because communication is crucial to politics, which has over-bearing influence on other spheres of democratic society. Framing underscores a characteristic presentational mode in news narration that points to media construction and audience consumption chain of influence. From empirical evidence in extant literature, framing of political speeches could have implications on the audience. This paper focused on the characteristic framing of political speeches in Nigerian newspapers and its possible implications on the reading public. The paper reviewed recent empirical works on framing and established that newspapers exhibit certain patterns of framing in their journalistic services of political surveillance, which could have consequences on the reading audience. The paper recommended that reporters of political news should always identify verbal and non-verbal frames in politicians' speeches and their potentials to manipulate the electorate. Newspaper organisations should regularly train and re-train their political news reporters in order to keep them abreast of emerging techniques in reportorial activities.

Keywords: Framing, Political speeches, Nigerian newspapers

Introduction

As a concept, framing is fast gaining research attention in communication and media studies. This is arguably because political communication has gained more relevance in social and political discourse. Political communication is described as an area of communication that studies the dynamic interaction among political actors - the media and the audience - having its principal focus on the nature of the relationship between the media and government on the one hand and media and society on the other (Burton, 2010). The research attention that framing has gained in political communication could be adduced to the importance of the mass media in modern democracies and the influence of media presentation of political issues on audience perception, opinions and attitudes. Framing underscores a characteristic presentational mode that points to media construction and audience consumption chain of influence.

Knudsen (2014) simply describes framing at a macro level as the way or pattern in which news is presented and at a micro level, "how certain elements in a news narrative would affect the reader" (p.209). Framing is a fast growing research subject in political communication, which scholars such as Aalberg, Stromback & de Vreese (2012) consider as one of the most fertile areas in recent research. In their accounts of reasons for the popularity of the subject, the authors argue from available empirical evidences

that framing of politics increases political distrust, has negative effects on citizens' knowledge acquisition, boosts public interest in politics, offers additional useful information and improves political participation. Framing is a research area about media contents and effects, which relates to how messages are presented (media frames) and the resultant influence of the patterned presentation on interpretation and/or perception (audience frames).

The relationship between media framing of political discourse and audience perception, opinion, attitude and/or actions has been established in empirical literature. For instance, Shrum (2002) contends that there is a relationship between media framing and perception of social reality. Entman, Mathes & Elicano (2009) reported that framing has consequences on public opinion by influencing aggregate indications of public opinion, perceived public opinion and anticipated majorities, all of which are crucial to political mobilisation. In their study of framing of politics, Aalberg, Stromback & de Vreese (2012) identify negative and positive consequences of framing in extant literature. On the negative side, framing is said to undermine political information and engagements, promote politicians' self-interests, distract the audience from substantive issues in stories and promote a spiral of cynicism. Positively, it stimulates attention to political issues and increases political participation. Oriola (2017) revealed that there was a significant relationship between patterns of framing and direction of public perception of President Buhari's anti-corruption crusade in Nigeria. From empirical evidences in extant literature, the characteristic manner of news construction (framing) of political speeches could have serious implications on the audience.

Meanwhile, Nigerian newspapers have demonstrated the character of vibrant nationalism from the period of their early history through independence to the struggles for democracy. According to Adesoji (2010), the disposition of the Nigerian press to issues of nationalism can be linked to its inclination to politics, which has continued to shape its functionality. In the assessment of Fadairo, Fadairo & Aminu (2014), there has been an increase in the coverage of political issues in Nigeria, especially corruption, since the emergence of the present democratic dispensation in 1999. In their coverage of political discourse, Nigerian newspapers employ narrative cues to present issues such as speeches of key political actors. The characteristic construction of political speeches, called framing, and its possible implications on the reading public are the focus of the discourse in this paper.

Concept, Process and Classification of Framing

The term 'framing' has its root in English 'frame', the two having their verb and noun forms. Snow, Benford, McCammon, Hewitt & Fitzgerald (2014) consider framing in its verb form as actions of political actors manifest in constructing meaning about issues. In its verb form, to frame literarily means to give shape to words, sentences, ideas; to surround something with a solid protecting edge; to put a border round something (Longman, 1989). Webster's Universal Dictionary & Thesaurus (2010) provides words that are synonymous to the verbal 'frame' to include build, compose, constitute, construct, form, make, mould, plan, shape, devise, fabricate and fashion. In essence these

action words explain what political actors do in respect of construction of meaning about political issues, which shape how people make sense of such issues. Politicians shape their speeches in a way to project their thoughts and images in both intended and unintended manners. Journalists follow political elites to report speeches delivered at events, moulding their reports based on their interactions with newsrooms' internal and external forces. Citizens as news consumers receive cues composed in stories, derive meaning from them and subsequently develop perceptions, opinions, attitudes and behaviour (favourable or unfavourable) about political actors and issues presented at events. Such outcomes may be direct or indirect as they may be moderated by personal and social variables within the audience.

'Frame' in its noun form means the shape, pattern or form given to something, the physical make-up of something, a firm border into which an object, expression, a message is set. Synonyms to the term's noun form include body carcass, framework, skeleton, shape, form, structure, scheme, condition, system, state and framing (Webster, 2010). In this form, it refers to something produced, created or constructed in the process of political communication. Frame has its production process, outcomes, typology and consequences. Its importance to political actors underscores the growing research interest in its analysis in the field of political communication. Beyond its etymology and literary definitions (which are of relevance), there is a need to generically clarify the concept of framing in a study such as this.

Framing as a media function entails the activities of professional communicators who intentionally or unintentionally construct media texts, which ultimately underscore media roles in the society. Framing, in this regard is defined by Entman, Mathes & Pellicano (2009 p.176) as "selecting some aspects of perceived reality and constructing messages that highlight connections among them in ways that promote a particular interpretation." This idea is in consonance with the explanation that news could be considered as a chip of diamond, the side within a person's view at a time determining his description of the object. Reporters' perceived reality, dictated by his personal and professional views of issues in the news, shapes the ways they construct news messages. More importantly the patterns of construction and presentation are connected to the way interpretations are projected by the mass media. Such patterns, if they become persistent among networks of professionals, represent a media function - intended or unintended. According to Entman, Mathes & Pellicano (2009), politicians, bloggers, editorial writers and pundits intentionally and strategically carry out framing to induce the audience to accept interpretations that would make them (framers) achieve their goals. According to Hallin & Mancini (2004) reporters and media editors are considered unintentional framers in the mainstream news media who do not have political goals to pursue, except those in party-affiliated and government-owned media. Oriola (2007) opines that this position may be oversimplified because journalists are members of the society who often encounter role conflicts in their professional conducts and such conflicts may lead to conscious framing in pursuance of some social, economic or political goals, regardless of organisational ownership type or party affiliation.

Framing can also be considered as a process. The process involves journalistic production, which can be considered at micro and macro levels (Knudsen, 2014). At the macro level, it refers to how news is presented and how the presentation affects contents while at the micro level, it entails how certain elements in news narrative affect the audience. This perspective considers both the outcomes of frame production as journalistic products and societal level consequences of framing. Scheufele (1999) & de Vreese (2005) underscore the importance of three stages of framing in understanding the concept: frame building, frame setting and societal level consequences. Frame building involves an interaction between internal and external factors that influence the structural attributes of news stories. The internal factors include reporters' and editors' personal and professional judgments, editorial policies, house styles and other organisational guidelines that determine what is reported and how the report is framed. External factors that determine framing include newsroom or individual reporters' interactions with political elites, advertisers, analysts, satirists, social commentators and social movements, all of whom are news sources. According to de Vreese (2005), a particular mix of the internal and external factors produces frames identifiable in news texts.

Frame setting refers to the interaction between media frames as outcomes of the frame production stage and individual's prior knowledge, schema, predisposition and/or attitude (de Vreese, 2005). D'Angelo (2018) terms this framing effect, which he says results through mediating factors such as prior knowledge, schemata, audience frames and official discourse. The fact that people rely on the mass media for news of the day, especially about events beyond their personal contacts, validates claims that the audiences learn about and interpret issues in news stories, which contain frames. Lippmann's (1922 p.104) assertion about how people learn about issues of public affairs attest to the foregoing, thus: "of public affairs, each of us sees very little and therefore, they remain dull and unappetising until somebody, with the makings of an artist, has translated them into a moving picture." The "artist" in this assertion figuratively refers to the reporter, editor or photojournalist while the "moving picture" refers to verbal and visual frames in news stories, which shape audience frames, applied in interpreting and evaluating issues, personalities and events. The audiences being active participants in the communication process moderate the effects that result with their prior knowledge and predisposition to the issue, event or personality.

Framing consequences can occur at individual or societal level. Individual perception, opinion, attitude or behaviour towards issues, events, places and personalities can be moulded or changed through an interaction between frames in communication and frames in thought (Druckman, 2011). At the societal level, frames may contribute to social level consequences such as political socialisation, decision making and collective actions (deVreese, 2005). Snow, Benford, McCammon, Hewitt & Fitzgerald (2014) observe that recent framing studies discovered framing influence on economic mobilisation, social movements and activism outcomes. The possible consequence of newspaper framing of political speeches in Nigeria is the focus of the discourse in this paper.

There are different classifications of framing in extant literature. Chong & Druckman (2007) distinguish between equivalence and emphasis framing. Equivalence framing entails presenting logically similar contents differently, some in positive and the others in negative narratives. Emphasis framing involves news narration of qualitatively distinct but potentially relevant considerations among different journalists. Applied to the discourse in this paper, emphasis framing occurs when different journalists or their newspapers report the same speech of a political actor from different angles, each using attributable differences in their narratives. Equivalence framing occurs when in the course of journalistic practices, Nigerian newspapers report a political actor's speech from the narrative of the content of campaign promises while others frame the same speech by reporting the presence or lack of innovative ideas in the speech. Emphasis framing is manifest in different Nigerians newspapers' reportage of the same politician's speech, one from the angle of the reactions it generated and the other from the perspective of the quality of speech delivered by the candidate.

Furthermore, de Vreese (2005) classifies framing into issue-specific and generic types. Issue-specific framing entails defining a problem, suggesting assessment and proffering solutions by presenting specific issues related to the problem. Generic framing entails presenting a topic from the perspective that cuts across different issues and events. In Nigeria for instance, presenting the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC) as a failed political party based on failure in specific areas of governance such as security, economy and anti-corruption amounts to issue-specific framing. A narrative on the opposition People's Democratic Party (PDP) as being responsible for the state of the nation, either now or earlier (without adducing reasons) amounts to generic framing. It should be noted that reporters may employ certain narrative devices – verbal and non-verbal – to construct news about speeches of political actors, thereby exhibiting certain types of framing. However, the news narratives delivered to the reading public carry certain types of frames and when such persist, certain framing patterns evolve in certain newspapers. The patterns of framing exhibited by certain newspapers have the potential to shape public perception, opinion, attitude and actions in certain directions.

Framing Theory: Evolution and Principles

This paper is anchored on framing theory, which is rooted in the discipline of psychology and sociology but has gained considerable applications and empirical investigations in communication and media studies. The foundation of scholarly works on the framing theory can be traced to Bateson (1972) in psychology, who establishes the roles of psychological frames in interpreting reality; and Goffman (1974) in sociology, who affirms that interpretive designs (referred to as frames) in messages constitute central elements in making meaning within a cultural belief system. To Goffman, frames are culturally oriented cues or devices used in constructing and interpreting reality and they are crucial in making sense of the world in all kinds of situations. Framing, the process or characteristic manner of using these devices to construct and interpret reality, was traditionally conceived from a phenomenological perspective that posits that the meaning derived from reality is based on individuals' perception based on the belief, knowledge

and experiences. After its discovery, framing as a subject has been widely studied in social and behavioural sciences such as, political science, law, economics, public opinion, journalism, communication and media studies (Lecheler & de Vreese, 2019). In communication and media studies, framing has gained considerable scholarly attention and it has stirred up immense empirical inquiry as news or media framing.

McQuail (2010 p.511) explains the media framing theory is attractive based on the principle that “an audience will be guided by journalistic frames in what they learn.” This implies that news sets the boundaries for meaning-making interaction in communication between the source and the receiver. In the interactional model of framing effect, McQuail (2010) agrees with Scheufele (1999) that there are four actors that shape the framing process: interested news sources, media organisations, journalists and media audiences. Message sources, especially political elites, deliberately or inadvertently employ verbal and non-verbal frames to deliver their speeches. Media organisations set frameworks through in-house editorial policies and house styles that guide news narration. Journalists employ verbal and non-verbal frames in conveying meaning about political speeches and events. Media audiences receive news information and interpret them with their mental or psychological frames, thereby leading to a meaning-making interaction. The underlying principle of the framing theory is that news information has attributes (frames) the meaning and salience of which are transferred in the process of selection, emphasis, exclusion and elaboration of news objects from journalists to media audiences (Griffin, 2012). Proponents of the framing theory postulate that an issue can be viewed from a variety of perspectives and constructed as having implications for multiple values or considerations (de Vreese, 2005; Chong & Druckman, 2007; Lecheler & de Vreese, 2019). News frames are used to conceptualise issues, organise everyday reality, lend meaning to an unfolding streak of events, and encourage a particular definition and interpretation of issues (Shah, Watts, Domke & Fan, 2002). Chong & Druckman (2007) argue that individual frames (frames in thought) are influenced by communication frames (social media frames) and the interaction between the two can shape people’s perception and behaviour. The narrative cues (frames) used in constructing information about political parties, candidates and the speeches of political actors can have implications on the perception of the audience or electorate (Oriola, Omotayo & Ajayi, 2022). Oriola, Omotayo & Ajayi (2022) further assert that the meanings, impressions or perception derived from framed speeches of political actors such as candidates, their campaigns managers and supporters can shape image in the estimation of the electorate and consequently public opinions, attitudes and voting behaviour for or against political candidates or their parties. The interaction between journalists and political actors who are news sources can shape what is reported and how, as well as the consequent public perception of the issues. Media organisations also set narrative frameworks through editorial policies, house styles and other guidelines into which journalists fix their stories. These shape news construction patterns which are expected to determine public perception.

Political Speeches

The field of politics is replete with planned and unplanned actions and events. Critical components of political events are political speeches. A political speech is considered a form of political language utilised to organise the minds and opinions of people, establish and maintain social relations, express feelings, sell ideas, policies and programmes in society (Hashim, 2015). The National Coalition Against Censorship (NCAC) (2018) defines a political speech as a commentary on matters of public concern. According to the US Supreme Court (2011), speech deals with matters of public concern when it can be fairly considered as relating to any matter of political discourse, social, or other concern to the community.

Arguably, among the most important messages from political actors to the people are speeches because they often include vital political party or public policy decisions for a democratic society. By giving a speech to the society a politician may not only justify political plans but also shape those plans in a way that makes them worthy of support among the target public and other critical stakeholders. That is why Simon & Xenos (2010, p. 367) maintain that a political speech is constructed in such a way as to accentuate aspects of the message that the leader thinks are likely to attract support. This is called framing and serves the purpose of promoting a certain “interpretation and evaluation” of a political issue by an audience (Entman 2004, p.26). However, unless people are present at political events where a speech is delivered, a politician cannot entirely determine how the public perceives the content of a speech. This is because the media are often represented at major political events where speeches are delivered and report such speeches. In their reportage, journalists adopt certain narrative frameworks to construct and present news about the political event, thereby promoting public interpretation, consideration and evaluation of the content of the speeches. Simon & Xenos (2010 p.367) added that “whether or not a presidential speech comes across the way a president communicated it, depends heavily on whether journalists pick up the president’s framing and put the emphasis on the same information that the president did”. Therefore, if media organisations do not do that, the public might not judge the political matter the way the politician intended, which could result in less support for the policy or programme the speech contains.

Furthermore, Hashim (2015) posits that political speeches are crucial aspects of the larger political discourse. Political speeches involve using words or lexical items to influence the polity at a broad level. Specifically, political speeches contain carefully selected lexical items that are meant to shape criteria of official decorum, emphasise political attitudes, manipulate public opinions, manufacture political consent and generate support to legitimise political power (Hashim, 2015). For the purpose of accomplishing these functions, political speeches are often carefully prepared using preferred structures and strategies. Political leaders often employ professional speech writers who are thoroughly trained wordsmiths and persuasive writers to compose their speeches.

The construction and delivery of political speeches involves the use of language to convey ideas and ideologies to receivers such as party members, supporters, the electorate and the larger public. Some of the receivers are present at the events where

speeches are made and thus receive the content firsthand. This category of people may derive interpretations as intended by the sources of the speeches. Their interpretation may also differ from the intended meaning due to their previous experience and communicative activities, including media use habits. People who receive the messages from the media will get interpretations and evaluation contained in the frames with which the messages are reported. Therefore, the roles of the media in shaping public understanding of the content of political speeches is considerable and this is a major focus of framing research termed framing effects or consequences. Hashim (2015) affirms that words and expressions are used or omitted in speeches and media construction of political speeches to affect meanings in various ways.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive and analytical research design based on a qualitative review of existing literature. This approach allows for the synthesis of theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence to establish the relationship between media framing, political speeches, and audience perception. Secondary data was sourced from reputable academic databases and libraries, with the search strategy prioritising scholarly articles, textbooks, and theses published between 1972 and 2022. The starting point of 1972 marks the foundational works of Bateson in framing theory. The search terms utilised to locate relevant literature included framing theory, political speeches, Nigerian newspapers, media effects, and political communication.

The literature selection process was guided by specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Studies were included if they provided empirical evidence on news framing patterns, analyzed the construction of political speeches, or examined the history and function of the Nigerian press. Sources that did not address mass media communication or lacked empirical or theoretical depth regarding the framing paradigm were excluded from the review. This ensured that only relevant and academically rigorous works formed the basis of the analysis. The selected literature was subjected to thematic analysis to identify patterns and relationships across the body of work. The reviewed sources were organised into three main themes: the conceptualisation and classification of framing, the nature and characteristics of political speeches, and empirical evidence of framing effects in both global and Nigerian contexts. This analytical method facilitated the identification of recurring patterns in journalistic practices and enabled examination of their potential consequences on the electorate. By structuring the analysis thematically, the study synthesises diverse scholarly perspectives while maintaining focus on the core research objectives concerning media framing and political communication.

Nigerian Newspapers in Politics

A newspaper is a mass medium which conveys news and other information about issues, events, products and services to the public at regular intervals. As a mass medium, newspapers are tools of information, education, opinion-moulding, persuasion, recreation, relaxation and entertainment. A typical general-purpose newspaper edition contains a variety of contents that serves these purposes. Okoye (2006) classifies

newspaper genres into news, meant to provide factual, timely and objective information about events; commentary, meant to express and coordinate opinions; advertisements, aimed at achieving persuasion in favour of products, services and ideas; and fiction which serves the diversion or entertainment function. In the category of news are straight news, features and news pictures while commentary includes editorials, editorial cartoons, opinion articles and letters to editors. All forms of advertisements, advertorials and supplements are meant to achieve persuasion while fiction, which includes short stories, serialised novels, poems and games are for entertainment (Okoye, 2006).

Globally, newspaper is the oldest traditional medium of mass communication coming behind book, ushered in by the invention of the movable type in Europe. In Nigeria, newspaper came far earlier than other media of mass communication as a private affair brought into the country by Christian missionaries. The pacesetters of Nigerian newspapers were *Iwe Irohin* founded in 1859 by Reverend Henry Townsend and *Anglo African* founded by Robert Campbell in 1863. Established initially as a tool of promoting literacy among natives, for the purpose of propagating the Christian faith, newspapers in Nigeria became instruments of nationalist struggles and combat against colonialism (Omu, 1978). In the struggle for nationalism, Nigerian newspapers exhibited various characters at different times reflecting the political struggles of each period. Daramola (2006) classifies political eras in Nigerian newspaper history into the periods of nationalism, consolidation, independence and post-independence. He states that by character, early Nigerian newspapers were political tools used by their founders and their political parties/movements to fearlessly reflect the moods of their time, vibrantly fight for eradication of social economic and political inadequacies of their time.

However, the post-independence Nigerian press lost its vibrancy and militancy earlier exhibited against British colonialists as they changed in orientation to assume regional and ethnic posture in support of their founders (Daramola, 2006). The parochial posture of the post-independence newspapers contributed to the fall of the first and second Republics in Nigeria, leading to coup d'état which led to the incursion of the military into governance. Successive military administrations in the country came to power and the Nigerian press became united again, forming a strong alliance against the military. The vibrancy and militancy of Nigerian newspapers against a common enemy was again displayed. Notably, the press contributed actively to the political struggles that led to the emergence of Nigeria's sovereignty in 1960 and the present democratic dispensation which began in 1999 (Adesoji, 2010). Oriola (2017) affirms that post-independence Nigerian newspapers were mostly commercial newspapers which actively participated in politics and governance at different phases of the country's history. Till date, newspapers play their roles in politics through coverage, analysis of, and commentary on political issues. In their content, newspapers present political issues of public interest using certain narrative cues called frames. Through framing, Nigerian newspapers have contributed immensely to political discourse by shaping issues that are considered important, generating public concerns, galvanising public debate, suggesting interpretations and evaluation, and shaping opinions about the issues.

Newspaper Framing of Political Discourse: An Empirical Review

Framing research has a relatively young history, originating from psychology with Bateson's (1955) work titled 'A Theory of Play and Fantasy'. Its root in sociology dates back to 1974 when Goffman published his seminal work titled 'Frame Analysis: An Essay on the Organisation of Experience' (Goffman, 1974). The application of framing research in communication and media studies could be traced to Entman's (1993) work titled, 'Framing: Toward a Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm'. In this paper, he positions framing as a research paradigm within the communication discipline. He conceptualises frames and framing, explains the functions of frames in communication as well as how they work. Entman's article has perhaps broadened framing research in communication and media studies. Lopez-Rabadan (2022) affirms that framing studies started gaining regular research attention in communication and media studies from the mid-1990s with Entman charting the course for research in journalistic framing by providing four realms of its manifestation, namely the sender of a message, message content, receivers and culture. In recent times, framing is situated largely in political communication sub-field of communication and media studies where it has gained considerable research attention in recent times. Some of the recent empirical studies on newspaper framing are hereby reviewed.

More broadly, Freyenberger (2013) conducted a study of how newspaper framing could globally affect the image of an individual. The study focused on Amanda Knox, a 20-year-old American foreign exchange student tried and imprisoned in Italy after the murder of her roommate, Meredith Kercher. Meredith's body was found behind a closed door while pictures of Knox and her boyfriend kissing and hugging were taken outside the house where the body was found. The study then analysed the portrayal of Knox in the American newspapers against her mention in newspapers outside America. Quantitative content analysis was conducted on 500 articles drawn from 34 newspapers around the world related to the case sourced from LexisNexis database, covering the period between November 2, 2007 – the date when the case began – and November 2, 2011 – the date chosen by the researcher for him to cover a precise four-year duration. Knox was found not guilty on October 3, 2011 and released from jail. A random sample of 500 articles from a population of 835 articles searched with the term 'Amanda Knox' on LexisNexis was drawn into the study. Findings of the study revealed that Amanda Knox was framed more positively in Australia, New Zealand, Thailand and South Korea than in the United States and Canada. Negative framing of Knox was also observed in the British and Irish media. As regards story placement, newspapers in Australia, New Zealand, Thailand, South Korea and China reported Knox more prominently than those in other countries but the North American newspapers mostly displayed her stories on their front pages.

A study of newspaper framing of corruption scandal in China was conducted by Yan & Liu (2016). The study was a framing analysis that aimed to examine how a corruption scandal about Chen Liangyu, a Chinese mainland high rank official who was the secretary of the Shanghai Municipal Committee (among other portfolios) was reported by the mainstream newspapers of Mainland and Hong Kong. The analysis focused on

four dimensions of framing analysis: definition of the issue, description of the issue, reason for and probability of corruption. The study adopted the frame competition approach to study framing patterns in newspapers with different ideologies, attitudes, stances and values based in three Chinese cities of Guangdong, Shanghai and Hong Kong. Selected from the Hong Kong media were *Ming Pa* and *Apple Daily*; from Guangdong were *Guang Zhou Daily* and *Southern Metropolis Daily*; and from Shanghai media were *Libertarian Daily* and *Xinnun Evening News*. A total of 321 news reports were drawn and analysed along the four dimensions of framing listed above. Findings of the study showed that Hong Kong newspapers stories on the corruption scandal accounted for the highest while Shanghai newspapers' reports ranked lowest in coverage. Also, the Hong Kong newspapers framed the scandal as power struggle, tip of iceberg and drama while the mainland media framed it as government's anti-corruption effort, system fallacy, individual morality and rotten apple. However, system fallacy and individual morality frames were employed more by Mainland media than the Hong Kong media. The foregoing show that media framing often follows the ideologies, values and stance of media organisations, which in turn are shaped by external socio-political factor of the environment within which they operate.

Oriola (2017) examined the relationship between selected national newspapers' framing patterns of the anti-corruption crusade of President Muhammadu Buhari's regime in Nigeria and public perception of the crusade as framing consequence. The study reported a significant relationship between the selected newspapers' patterns of framing and the direction of public perception about the issue. Most of the stories reported in the selected national newspapers were framed as issue-specific, exposure of wrongdoing, critical of President Goodluck Jonathan's administration and accusing the People's Democratic Party (PDP). Public perception was reported to have followed the same direction, with audience's political knowledge and party affiliation having significant moderating effects on the relationship between framing and perception of the anti-corruption crusade. The study also found out significant moderating effects of political knowledge and political party affiliation in the relationship between patterns of framing and framing perception.

Osah & Jinmi-Ahisu (2021) investigated the relationship between media framing and election violence in Nigeria's fourth Republic. The study adopted qualitative content analysis to examine how news stories about elections in Nigeria were framed in three national newspapers – *The Punch*, *This Day* and *The Guardian*. The study found out a direct connection between newspaper framing of political issues, especially campaigns and election violence in Nigeria. The study discovered the use of metaphorical expressions by political actor and such expressions were reported in three selected national newspapers. This amounted to framing which led to different interpretations among the electorate and when certain interests were displeased, violence ensued.

Oriola, Omotayo & Ajayi (2022) analysed pattern of framing of Nigeria's 2019 Presidential election in five national newspapers, examined direction of perception of the framed issues, and determined the relationship between perception and voting pattern in Tai Solarin University of Education (TASUED), Ogun State, Nigeria. The study adopted

correlational descriptive research design which combined content analysis with survey; selected samples of 92 editions of *The Guardian*, *The Punch*, *Vanguard*, *Nigerian Tribune* and *Daily Sun* published between November 18, 2018 and February 21, 2019 for content analysis; and 541 respondents from TASUED community for questionnaire survey. Findings showed that the campaign stories, dominated by the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC), were mostly reported using issue-specific frames and supportive of the party. Respondents perceived framing of the campaigns in the selected newspapers as personality-focused, dominated by the APC, projected name-calling and mudslinging among political actors, subjective and unhealthy for Nigeria's growing democracy. Voting was motivated by media reportage and candidates' personalities. The study found a significant relationship between the direction of perception of newspaper framing of the campaigns and voting pattern among members of TASUED community. Political party affiliation had significant moderating effect on the relationship between perception and voting pattern among respondents.

Conclusion

Extant literature is replete with empirical evidences of certain patterns of framing exhibited in the media in the course of performing journalistic function of surveillance of the political environment. Nigerian newspapers cannot be absolved of the manifestation of framing patterns in the construction of news narratives and presentation of such about speeches of political actors such as politicians, political candidates, political campaign managers or handlers and supporters of political parties and their candidates. It should be noted that the interactions between reports and the political actors who are news sources result into news framing as the actors intentionally or otherwise shape their speeches in their quest to generate public support. The speeches so presented about political issues are constructed using narrative cues and reported by journalists in their respective newspapers, thereby exhibiting certain patterns of framing. The framing patterns so exhibited have the potential to determine meaning-making as the reading public consume news content of newspapers. The result of the news production-consumption chain is framing consequence, manifest in public perception of, opinion on, attitude towards and actions about issues in the speeches of the political actors. Therefore, the empirical evidence reported in this paper lends credence to the validity of framing theory, the manifestation of framing patterns in newspapers, Nigerian newspapers inclusive, and the possible consequences of framing on readers of political news stories. The discourse in this paper should thus guide journalists in separating facts from opinions and other promotional contents as they construct their news stories. In their interactions with political actors, they should always identify verbal and non-verbal frames in politicians' speeches and their potentials to be used to manipulate the electorate.

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